

STRUCTURAL FAILURE IN FILAMENT WOUND RIGHT CIRCULAR CYLINDRICAL SHELLS SUBJECTED TO BIAXIAL EXTERNAL PRESSURE

F. Spicola, N. Dubois, W. Tucker
& J. Butts

Naval Undersea Warfare Center
Newport Division
Newport, Rhode Island (USA)

ABSTRACT

Variations in compressive strength as a function of fiber layup and wall thickness are considered for filament wound right circular cylindrical shells subjected to biaxial external pressure. Test data from external hydrostatic pressure failure tests for a series of cylindrical test samples is presented. Comparison with smeared property buckling predictions (BOSOR5) is provided. Significant differences between test data and smeared property analyses are discussed. A first step in developing an analytical failure prediction algorithm is presented.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Predicting failure in externally pressurized filament wound composite cylindrical shells remains extremely difficult if not impossible without significant full scale testing on an application by application basis. Present analysis methods involve smeared properties for distinct laminates, interlaminar shear, and global buckling. These methods are ineffectual except for very thin walled cylinders (Diameter-to-wall thickness ratio on the order of 50 to 1 or greater).

This paper addresses the externally pressurized composite shell problem by presenting the results from a set of failure tests for several cylindrical test samples. These samples are characterized by varying wall thicknesses (all with less than 50-to-1 thickness-to-diameter ratios) and orthogonal continuous fiber layups. Also introduced is an initial effort to analyze such shells. The analysis considers hoop stress distribution through the thickness by superimposing membrane compressive stresses with maximum bending stresses caused by increasing eccentricity with increasing pressure.

2.0 STRENGTH TESTS AND ANALYSIS

Two sets of ultimate external pressure tests were conducted with respect to cylindrical test samples. One involved 0/90 carbon filament wound layups with several wall thicknesses and a second involved 0/90/90 carbon filament wound layups with several wall thicknesses. Experimental results are presented, along with an

initial quick-look bending analysis of a mid-span shell section. This analysis provides insight into elevated inner layer compressive stresses in an, $n = 2$, pre-buckle shell deflection. See figure (1) for the basic dimensions of a typical cylindrical test sample, and figure (2) for the test load format and typical test sample end conditions.

Figure 1. Cylindrical Test Sample - Basic Nominal Dimensions

Figure 2. Cylindrical Test Sample with Simply Supported Ends Subjected to External Hydrostatic Pressure

2.1 Ultimate External Pressure Tests The first set of tests included cylinders of the basic dimensions shown in figure (1), Inner Diameter = 4.4 inches and Length = 8.5 inches. These test samples were filament wound with AS4 Carbon fibers and Union Carbide's ERL 2258 epoxy resin. The layup format was one hoop layer to one longitudinal layer (0/90) evenly dispersed, and the wall thicknesses ranged from 0.1315 to 0.2485 inches. See table (1). The average fiber volume fraction was 60% and the average void content was less than 2%.

Each sample was externally pressurized in a hydrostatic compression chamber with end bulkheads that provided simply supported end conditions. All samples were pressurized to failure. All failures were characterized by a single longitudinal failure line with a fracture plane at 45 degrees though the wall. See figure (3). The inner surface of each sample was significantly delaminated in the mid-span region at the fracture. The indication was that failure began at the inner surface in the mid-span region, and was compressive in nature. There was no evidence of global buckling. If so, the test samples would have broken into a collection of small pieces, as is observed in experiments with very thin-walled carbon cylinders.

The observed failure pressures for the 0/90 tests were compared to BOSOR5 predicted buckling pressures for an orthotropic cylinder. See table (1) and figure (4). BOSOR5 is a finite difference algorithm for axi-symmetric buckling pressure and compressive stress predictions in isotropic or orthotropic multi-layer cylindrical shells.

The second set of tests included cylinders with constituents, basic dimensions, fiber contents, and void contents very similar to the first set of tests. The wall thicknesses ranged from 0.1075 to 0.246 inches; and the layup format (the only major parameter which was significantly different) was 0/90/90, two hoop layers to one longitudinal layer. The characteristics of the fractures were the same as the first tests, and the relationship with respect to the BOSOR5 analysis was similar to the first tests. See table (2) and figure (5).

Figure 3. Typical Fracture Geometry in Cylindrical Test Sample Following Failure under External Hydrostatic Pressure

IDENTIFICATION NUMBER	LENGTH (INCHES)	INSIDE DIAMETER (INCHES)	WALL THICKNESS (INCHES)	PREDICTED SMEARED PROPERTY BUCKLING PRESSURE (PSI)	OBSERVED EXTERNAL FAILURE PRESSURE (PSI)
090130-2	8.505	4.405	0.1315	1775	1500
090130-6	8.505	4.405	0.1315	1775	1600
090190-1	8.5065	4.405	0.191	5300	3600
090190-3	8.5065	4.405	0.1885	5300	3500
090190-6	8.5077	4.405	0.191	5300	3600
090250-2	8.5077	4.407	0.2485	7950	5800
090250-3	8.5089	4.407	0.242	7950	5800
090250-6	8.5077	4.407	0.240	7950	5700

Table 1. Ultimate External Hydrostatic Pressure for 0/90 Filament Wound AS4 Carbon/ERL 2258 Epoxy Cylindrical Test Samples of Various Wall Thicknesses with Simply Supported Ends

Figure 4. Ultimate External Hydrostatic Pressures for 0/90 Cylindrical Test Samples Compared to Smearing Property Buckling Predictions (BOSOR5)

IDENTIFICATION NUMBER	LENGTH (INCHES)	INSIDE DIAMETER (INCHES)	WALL THICKNESS (INCHES)	PREDICTED SMEARED PROPERTY BUCKLING PRESSURE (PSI)	OBSERVED EXTERNAL FAILURE PRESSURE (PSI)
09090113-2	8.5089	4.404	0.1075	1850	975
09090113-3	8.5097	4.404	0.1075	1850	1000
09090203-3	8.5109	4.408	0.197	5650	4000
09090203-4	8.5113	4.408	0.195	5650	4000
09090203-6	8.5101	4.408	0.197	5650	3900
09090252-2	8.5097	4.406	0.244	8550	5700
09090252-5	8.5077	4.406	0.2445	8550	5800
09090252-6	8.5089	4.406	0.246	8550	5800

Table 2. Ultimate External Hydrostatic Pressure for 0/90/90 Filament Wound AS4 Carbon/ERL 2258 Epoxy Cylindrical Test Samples of Various Wall Thicknesses with Simply Supported Ends

Figure 5. Ultimate External Hydrostatic Pressures for 0/90/90 Cylindrical Test Samples Compared to Smear Property Buckling Predictions (BOSOR5)

2.2 Initial Bending Stress Analysis In figure (6), Pressure failure results from tables (1) and (2) are plotted together along with BOSOR5 buckling pressure predictions. BOSOR5 buckling pressures are separated as would be expected - with the 0/90/90 cylinder buckling predictions higher than those for the 0/90 samples. However, experimental results for the same cylinders show failure pressures that fall on the same curve - independent of fiber layup format and with a trend quite different from the buckling pressure analysis. In light of previous experiments, see references [1], [2], [3], and [4], with ASTM compression samples, three-point bending samples and thick walled filament wound cylinders, these observations were not surprising even if not predictable.

It is clear that a mode other than global buckling accounted for the failures observed. All samples tested should have failed in global buckling well below smeared property compressive strength predictions. Smeared property compressive strength predictions would be based on experimental results obtained in references [1], [2], and [3] for prismatic beam and column samples, as well as engineering data sheets from the Hercules Corporation. However, the samples failed well below global buckling predictions. This observation indicates that some local phenomenon is causing failure, and that there is a need for additional analysis to account for that phenomenon.

An attempt was made to gain some insight into high stress regions in cylinders subjected to external pressures. It was assumed that there would always be some small initial eccentricity of 0.001 to 0.002 inches for any cylinder to be tested. With an initial eccentricity integral in a finite element model of the mid-span of a representative test cylinder, a hybrid progressive finite difference analysis was performed. This analysis showed that large compressive stresses due to a combination of membrane shell stresses and bending stresses are realized very quickly at relatively low level external pressures. These compressive stresses appear to have the potential to reach microbuckling limits before global buckling can occur in some geometries. See figures (7) and (8). In figure (7), the eccentricity is assumed to enlarge the vertical diameter and shorten the horizontal diameter; thus creating an elevated stress area at the ends of the major or enlarged diameter.

3.0 CONCLUDING REMARKS

At the present time the development of large scale filament wound structures for external hydrostatic pressure environments is extremely difficult and expensive. There is never a high level of confidence in such designs without extensive full scale testing and significantly elevated safety factors. While the experimental results presented in this paper do not solve the myriad of problems, they do however, expose a more complex problem set than that which has been assumed to date. Developers cannot assume that all the discrepancies that have been encountered are attributable to fabrication problems, interlaminar shear, or inconsistencies at the micromechanical level of the structure. The basic physics of failure has not yet been exposed. While the community continues to pursue better quality fabrications, the answer to the dilemma of unpredictability lies in exposing the failure mode.

Figure 6. Ultimate External Hydrostatic Pressures for 0/90/90 and 0/90 Cylindrical Test Samples Compared to Smear Property Buckling Predictions (BOSOR5)

Figure 7. Finite Element Model of the Mid-Span Area of a typical Filament Wound Test Cylinder

Figure 8. Mid-Span Bending (Compressive) Stress Analysis for a Nominal AS4/ERL 2258 Test Cylinder with a 0.252 Inch Wall Thickness versus External Hydrostatic Pressure

4.0 REFERENCES

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